

Effectiveness of Digital Multimedia Based Pedagogical Package to Enhance the Factors on Perceptual Understanding and Retention Ability

^{1*}Corresponding Author S. Floral Jeya, Research scholar, Department of Education, CDOE, Alagappa University, Karaikudi. Tamil Nadu, India.

²Dr. AR. Saravanakumar, Associate professor, Department of Education, CDOE, Alagappa University, Karaikudi. Tamil Nadu, India.

Abstract

This research investigates a didactic breakthrough in math instruction the use of digital multimedia packages and instruction. It contrasts multimedia with traditional teaching approaches with an emphasis on student viewpoints, information retention, and acquisition. In complicated domains where typical frontal instruction is insufficient, the study highlights the significance of learning diversity and individualization. High potential for applying this concept is provided by digital multimedia and education; yet, the effects are contingent upon particular learning activities, leading to inconsistent findings in previous studies. In one research, thirteen-year-old primary school students participated in an experimental group that received instruction using digital multimedia and teaching while the control group received instruction using traditional methodologies. Post-tests were used to assess student's grasp of the subject matter, emphasizing the significance of on-going research in comprehending this finding. Three months later, a follow-up assessment was conducted. To evaluate how well knowledge acquired through education and digital multimedia is retained. Thirteen tasks were completed, six of which dealt with polygon area and perimeter, and the last job was also concerned with these topics..

Keywords; *Digital multimedia, Innovative teaching methods, Perception, Retention, Multimedia Instruction, and Educational technology.*

Introduction

Traditional classes that promote frontal learning for the entire class may not be sufficiently engaging to all pupils, even with exceptionally outstanding implementation especially when it comes to more complex subjects. Consequently, in order for students to meet the learning objectives of modern education, teachers need to be able to effectively integrate various instructional methods and within-class student grouping strategies. They also need to be open to new ideas in didactics and actively seek out teaching strategies that maximize students mental and emotional engagement.

According to Valencic Zuljan and Plesec Gasparic (2018), multimedia and teaching is a didactic innovation with a great deal of potential for putting the didactic principles of differentiation and individualization into practice. Because it has a positive effect on students' academic achievement and can be greatly tailored to meet their learning needs. It has thus garnered a great deal of interest from researchers and practitioners. To further investigate this innovation, there are several explanations available. First, as stated by Forester et al. (2022), "there is limited evidence on the relationship between engagement in pre-class video watching and later achievement, particularly in knowledge retention in the digital multimedia (Saravanakumar, AR., 2011)". This is especially true in the Slovenian context, where there is a dearth of research on the effects of multimedia and teaching on academic achievements. Second, studies on the efficacy of this innovation present contradictory findings. While some studies assert that the effects are neutral, many studies confirm positive effects on students knowledge (Chen et al., 2017). Therefore, more research is required, possibly leading to a clearer identification of the determinants.

Third, although the majority of research is conducted at the secondary and tertiary education levels (Al Ghawail, E. A., & Ben Yahia, S., 2021), primary school education has received less attention, which is why our focus has been on this educational level. Were curious about how students perceived digital multimedia and instruction, as well as how acquired knowledge and retention compared between traditional and digital multimedia instruction. Because of this, we created an experiment wherein a group of thirteen-year-old primary school students received traditional instruction in mathematics, while a second group received the same instruction through the use of digital multimedia learning and teaching methods. Accordingly,

the goal of the study was to compare how differently the two groups retained their newly acquired knowledge and how differently they had learned the subject. Additionally, a questionnaire was intended to be used to ascertain the student's opinions of the digital multimedia instruction and teaching methodology. Our study of multimedia instruction and learning in elementary schools is significant because it adds to our understanding of this innovation at a level of education that has received less attention. Furthermore, our conclusions are based on an experiment's findings rather than just the teachers' and students self-reported opinions. Our unique contribution is that we assessed students' knowledge retention after three months of effectiveness of multimedia learning and teaching, in addition to their immediate knowledge following the intervention. This gives us a different viewpoint on the efficacy of digital multimedia instruction and teaching. The article has the following structure (Padmini Devi, KR., & Saravanakumar, AR., 2018). Our research questions and the conceptual framework are presented in the following section. The methodological framework for the study is then explained in the section that follows. The section that follows, where we present and talk about the results, comes after this. The last section offers a summary of the findings, outlines the study's limitations, and makes recommendations for additional research on the subject.

Multimedia Packages

Students can achieve their learning objectives more rapidly and effectively by using media. Chalkboards, charts, radios, TVs, films, modules and videos are examples of common teaching aids. Some of these media are used to help them get ready for their adventures. Some media make learning in small groups or alone easier. As a result, teaching and learning are made easier for the teacher when they employ a range of media. The instructor also had the option to combine different media. (Floral Jeya, S. and Saravanakumar, AR.2018) All the materials required to teach a specific subject are included in multimedia packages. Access to the instructional resources is granted after careful planning. It provides learning experiences in order to meet the predetermined goals and produce the desired learning outcomes. These resources have been evaluated and found to be effective when used as intended in classrooms. The teacher needs to use a variety of resources in a cohesive way.

Retention

The ability to store knowledge in memory, or more specifically, the ability to retain the learning and experience-related benefits that facilitate recognition or recall, is known as retention. Retention is the quality of having something retained. "Retention" refers to the ability of a learner to hold onto the knowledge they have acquired over time. It covers Retention is the capacity to retrieve and use the information and abilities acquired during the the procedures for storing, encoding, and later retrieving data from long-term memory. learning process. It is an essential part of learning. Retention is impacted by the mental strain (cognitive load) that students experience during the learning process. (Saravanakumar AR, & Kalimuthu S., 2018). Teachers can support students' cognitive processing by minimizing pointless mental processing (extraneous cognitive load) and enhancing fruitful learning processes. Consequently, this raises the possibility that data will be stored and encoded in long-term memory..

Review of the Literature

Given the world we live in, which is full of blending cultures and on-going change, there is a greater need than ever for creativity in education. Introducing innovation and change is closely linked to pedagogical challenges, which educators must be prepared to confront and overcome.

Didactic innovations are intentional and creative efforts by researchers and teachers to improve pedagogical practice. They involve a system of pedagogical, social, organizational, and economic measures that aim to improve work quality, use resources efficiently, and democratize school relations. They also foster creativity, encourage evaluation, and find motivating factors for students and teachers. Mantic defines didactic innovation as a synchronized system of pedagogical, social, and economic measures.

Many factors make dialectic innovation necessary, such as the speed at which information becomes obsolete and changes, the variety and flux of student needs, the increasing demands placed on education, and the results of studies on teaching and learning (such as a meta-analysis of studies on instruction, learning differentiation, and individualization). Pedagogical innovations have often been associated with ICT use because student-centered instructional models (e.g., Bakkenes et al., 2010) have become more and more popular

in recent decades. These models emphasise active and self-regulated student learning. Here, the multimedia and teaching approach, one of the didactic innovations, is examined.

Table 1. Comparison between traditional instruction and digital multimedia instruction and teaching

	Traditional instruction	Digital Multimedia teaching
Learning space	studying the curriculum during class at school	Learning the material at home
Class time	Content is taught in class.	Discussions, projects, and problem-solving using what the pupils have learnt at home are done during class time.
Instructional stages	At school, practice, exercise, and repetition happen on a smaller scale.	At school, practice, exercise, and repetition happen on a bigger scale.
Direct/ indirect learning forms of students grouping	Direct learning in a collaborative learning environment,	Direct learning in a personal learning environment
Instructional methods	The explanation method is more commonly used in clear	The conversation method is more commonly used in class.

Since digital multimedia education and teaching are still relatively new pedagogical innovations, it is important to evaluate this approach's effectiveness from a number of angles. In our study, we have opted to focus on the students' perceptions of this novel teaching approach, information retention, and learning outcomes. The current study sought to determine whether there were any differences in the seventh grade students' (13-year-olds') knowledge of polygons between the groups that received traditional instruction and the group that received instruction using digital multimedia strategies. For the purpose of finishing the investigation,

Research questions:

First research question: What are the differences between the knowledge that students learn from traditional instruction and from instruction that uses digital multimedia training and teaching methods?

Research Question 2: What differences exist between the two groups' students' retention of recently learned material?

Research Question 3: How satisfied are students with digital multimedia instruction and training, and what are the advantages and disadvantages, etc.?

Methodology

Design

In educational research, descriptive and causal-experimental approaches are employed. The methodical approach. Used the qualitative method in part to analyse the answers to the open-ended questions on the questionnaire.

Participants

The research sample consisted of 55 seventh-graders, or 13-year-olds, from the selected primary school. The participants in this convenience non-probability sample were chosen from two concurrent seventh-grade classes (7.a and 7.b). The pupils in the two parallel classrooms were split into two groups before being allocated to one of the two groups in the experiment. Based on their prior knowledge, to enable adaptable differentiation in the learning environment.

Divide each portion in half as well. two groups: a control group (CG) and an experimental group (EG). This time, split the class into two groups of ten students each, one for the experimental group and the other for the control group based on the alphabetical order of surnames. As Figure 1 shows, the groups were mixed based on gender (M = male; F = female)..

Data Collection

Experiment

An educational experiment was carried out to collect data. first. After the experiment was finished, the topic of polygons was discussed in the maths class. Parental consent was obtained prior to the experiments commencing, and participation was completely voluntary. Used a pre-test, a post-test, and a second post-test to gather data. only examined the effects of digital multimedia instruction and training on learning outcomes in this study. Therefore, it was imperative to keep control over every aspect and exert every effort to reduce the impact of digital multimedia instruction and training.

Consequently, the students were split into two experimental and control groups based only on last names, rather than any other factor that might have been related to their motivation, prior knowledge, or other traits. The post-tests were administered simultaneously to both groups; the first was given just before the school year ended, and the second was given over the summer, when it was thought that the children would have had the least amount of opportunity to interact with one another.

The same pre-test, which assessed the students' past understanding of the subject, was given to each group prior to the start of the experiment. Next was the main part of the experiment. Students in the control group were able to experiment with the new material in class because the courses were taught in a traditional way. The experimental group used a different approach that involved instruction and digital multimedia teaching. In order to replicate the explanation that the first group received at school as closely as possible, a pre-recorded video explanation was made.

The experimental group of students was instructed to watch the movie at home and take notes. Ensuring that the students viewed the film at home was the only practical application of this technique. In the modified lesson at school, the teacher's main job was to encourage the students to study and to work together by giving them different practice and repetition opportunities.

Additionally, both groups received an extra practice and repetition session (the curriculum of both lessons was as identical as feasible). Two or three days following the educational experiment, a post-test was given, with questions that were at least somewhat similar to the pre-test. The post-test was completed by the control group as well as the experimental group. After about three months, a second post-test was given to determine the retention of the learned material.

Three tests: pre-, post-, and second post-

Three tests were used to assess the students' knowledge: a pre-test, a post-test, and an additional post-test. Each of the three tests consisted of thirteen activities; the first six focused on polygon perimeters, while the second six addressed polygon area. The last, more difficult task concerned the perimeter and area of polygons. The maximum score for each test was thirty.

Written survey

Furthermore, a brief survey was finished. at the end of the trial to determine how satisfied the students in the experimental group were with the multimedia instruction and teaching approach. The questionnaire was divided into four sections. In the first section, students evaluated multimedia instruction and teaching using a Likert scale. In the second section, a dichotomous question was used to find out if the students would be willing to participate in a class that used digital multimedia instruction and teaching methods in the future. In the third section, they indicated how much more they would participate in class if digital smultimedia training and teaching were used going forward. In the final section, they used open-ended questions to write down their thoughts on the advantages and disadvantages of the approach.

Data Analysis

The two sets of data that were analysed were those that were gathered using the questionnaire, post-test, second post-test, and pre-test. The statistical analyses, both inferential and descriptive, were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics 25. To begin the statistical analysis, combine the two experimental groups into a single experimental group and the two control groups into a single control group. As much as possible, try to group the parts together so that the final results of the analysis are less affected by the prior knowledge of each part. The performance indicator used in each analysis was the total number of points obtained in the selected test. The pre-test, post-test, and second post-test data for the experimental group and the control group were all normally distributed.

Table 2. Normality test for pre-test, post-test and second post-test scores for

Shapiro- Wilk test	Statistics			Df	Significance		
	Pre-test	Post Test	Second post test		Pre test	post test	Second post test
EG	0.966	0.964	0.971	26	0.319	0.295	0.430
CG	0.986	0.972	0.971	26	0.785	0.426	0.420

The score variances for both groups were similar (see Table 3). Additionally, because each group had more than 15 observations, we could use the independent t-test to assess the statistical significance of the differences in accomplishment between the two groups. Similar to this, since the pre-, post-, and second post-test data had a normal distribution and satisfied the $n > 20$ minimum number of observations requirement, a dependent t-test could be applied.

Table 3. Homogeneity of variances test for pre-test, post-test and second post- test scores for experimental and control group

	Levene statistic	df1	df2	Statically significance
Pre-test	0.196	1	50	0.671
Post-test	0.098	1	50	0.769
Second post-test	0.796	1	50	0.381

Furthermore, in the event that the influence of prior knowledge was eliminated, we conducted a covariance analysis to ascertain the differences in the knowledge that students in the experimental group and control group acquired. The frequency distributions of the responses to each item in the first three sections of the questionnaire were examined using IBM SPSS Statistics 25, which assisted in the quantitative analysis of the survey data. We used a more qualitative method and performed a content analysis of the survey responses from the students in order to analyse the questions from the fourth section.

And Manage the Variations in Students Acquired Knowledge of Experimental Groups:

To determine the differences in knowledge between students taught using a digital multimedia instruction and teaching strategy and students taught using a traditional approach, a pre-test was used to first assess students prior knowledge in the experimental group and control group.

Table 4. Descriptive statistics for pre-test achievement for experimental and control groups

	Mean	Frequency	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum
EG	19.9038	26	5.09531	6.51	28.00
CG	19.6192	26	5.38863	8.00	29.00
Total	19.1115	52	5.19609	6.51	29.00

The study found that there was no statistically significant difference in the pre-test average scores ($t(50) = 0.27$, $p = 0.798$). The study's findings showed that there were no statistically significant differences in the pre-test accomplishment means ($p > 0.05$). The results of the SPSS analysis are shown in Table 5. carried out additional covariance analysis in an attempt to find any differences between the knowledge that students in the experimental group and control group had acquired should the impact of prior knowledge be eliminated.

Table 5. Analysis of covariance for post-test achievement for experimental and control groups

Source	Tpe-11 sum of square	df	Mean square	F	Statistical significance
Corrected model	697.1707	2	353.553	24.777	0.000
Intercept	119.380	1	119.380	7.909	0.007
Points and CG	687.063	1	687.065	46.550	0.000
EG and CG	1.444	1	1.414	0.094	0.762
Error	739.100	50	15.084		
Total	22366.250	53			
Corrected Total	1436.207	52			

When the impact of prior knowledge was removed from the equation, Table 5 demonstrates that there was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in the post-test results between the experimental group and the control. Determine that there was no discernible difference between the two groups' short-term knowledge tests conducted right after the experiment based on the data that was collected. The lack of empirical evidence regarding the positive effects of digital multimedia instruction and learning was brought to light by (Abeysekera, L., & Dawson P., 2014). Empirical research has so far produced mixed results regarding this methodology's impact on students' learning outcomes. While some studies and meta-analyses find no statistically significant differences in learning outcomes when compared to traditional instruction, other studies (Bell, M.R., 2015) find no statistically significant differences in learning outcomes.

Can draw the conclusion that, in our instance, despite some encouraging findings about the effects of multimedia instruction and teaching on academic achievement, the multimedia instruction and teaching approach proved to be just as successful in terms of test results as the traditional approach. Consistent with the findings, some studies have not discovered any statistically significant differences between the experimental and control groups.

Analyse the effects of our experimental intervention over the long term and speculate about possible causes for the results we observed in the next subsection.

The Variations in Students Knowledge Retention between the Experimental and Control Groups

To determine any differences in the retention of recently learned information, students in the two groups were first evaluated based on their performance on the post-test and then based on their performance on the second post-test for the experimental group and control group.

Table 6: Post-test achievement descriptive statistics for the experimental and control groups

	Mean	Frequency	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum
EG	19.823	26	5.15094	10.50	28.00
CG	21.000	26	5.74256	11.00	30.00
Total	19.9712	52	5.28818	10.50	30.00

Table 6 demonstrates that although there was a slight difference in the average post-test scores between the control and experimental groups ($M = 21.00$, $SE = 5.74$ vs. $M = 19.84$, $SE = 5.15$), the differences were not statistically significant ($t(50) = -0.04$, $p = 0.969$). The average score of the experimental groups on the second post-test, however, was slightly higher than that of the control groups ($M = 17.08$, $SE = 5.98$) ($M = 18.58$, $SE = 5.07$). However, Table 7 indicates that $t(50) = 0.93$, $p = 0.357$ indicates that the differences were not statistically significant.

Table 7. Characteristics of the experimental and control groups' performance on the second post-test

	Mean	Frequency	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum
EG	18.5808	26	5.07059	9.50	27.00
CG	17.0877	26	5.98202	7.50	27.50
Total	17.7692	52	5.51687	7.50	27.50

When comparing the student's performance on the control group (CG) post-test and second post-test, their average score on the latter ($M = 17.07$, $SE = 5.98$) was lower than their post-test ($M = 21.00$, $SE = 5.74$). The achievement differences were found to be statistically significant at $t(25) = 3.30$ and $p = 0.003$.

Comparing the experimental group's (EG) performance in the post-test and the second post-test, however, reveals a smaller difference in average scores between the two ($M = 18.58$, $SE = 5.07$) and the post-test ($M = 19.94$, $SE = 5.13$). Between these two, there is statistically little difference. Using $p = 0.072$ and $t(25) = 1.88$.

As a result, after doing research, we found that students who were taught using a traditional method had less resilient familiarity with the material than those who were not. Knowledge retention is described as being intrinsically very significant by (Marentic Pozarnik, P., 2011) as one of the main attributes of high-quality information. The differences between problem-based learning and conventional teaching techniques are examined in this study.

It's interesting that both authors came to the same conclusions even though this case differs from the previous one. Test results taken immediately after the intervention did not show any differences, but a year later it was evident that the students who had employed the creative strategy had done better. It's possible that the experimental group's better knowledge retention is due to the fact that this method allows each student to choose their own learning pace by customising it for them.

This has to do with how Bloom popularised the idea of "mastery learning" in the 1960s, as mentioned in (Eppard, J., & Rochdi, A., 2017). This idea may be seen as something that promotes such innovation even if it has nothing to do with multimedia teaching and learning. Since students in our case learn the material at their own pace when receiving multimedia instruction and teaching, we assume that this improved knowledge retention is due to mastery learning. The adjustments that multimedia teaching and instruction make to the learning phases particularly in relation to the order of the stages would be another explanation for this. While learning new material is shifted to the home environment, more time is spent at school on training, repetition, and practice. Naturally, phases that are closely related to information retention include training, practice, and repetition. If students engage in it more actively under the teacher's guidance, this could be beneficial for the class..

Prior research has yielded comparable results, indicating that digital multimedia-based instruction and teaching facilitate the retention of information (Graham et al., 2019). Caution that there are several approaches, exercises, and teaching strategies that can be used to implement multimedia and teaching, not all of which will inevitably result in higher-quality content. Therefore, it is crucial that educators design lessons that will pique students' interest, help them think critically and creatively, interact with the subject matter, and solve problems. Students' increased engagement in unusual and novel learning situations might also be a factor in their better knowledge retention. This will be discussed in the next section along with the fact that students are more driven to study and have a more positive attitude towards learning.

Students Views of Teaching and Digital Multimedia Instruction

Students were asked four sets of questions to find out what they thought about teaching and multimedia instruction: (a) Did they think the approach was satisfactory? (b) Would they like to see teaching and learning done this way in the future? (c) Would they participate more in class if the teaching and digital multimedia instruction approach were used more often? (d) What aspects of the teaching and digital multimedia instruction approach did they like and didn't like, or where they saw benefits and drawbacks?

Table 8: Frequency distribution of students' agreement with the statement regarding the teaching and learning of multimedia

Level of agreement Item	I do not agree	I partly agree	I agree	I completely agree
1. I liked learning by watching recorded explanations more than listening to the explanations in class.				
Frequency	2	8	8	8
Percentage	7.78%	30.87%	30.87%	30.87%
2. My motivation for work was higher.				
Frequency	6	8	8	4
Percentage	20.13%	30.87%	30.87%	15.38%
3. It was easier to follow the explanation in the video than in school.				

Frequency	2	4	12	8
Percentage	7.78%	15.47%	46.15%	30.87%

4. The classes that were done face-to-face were more interesting than usual.				
Frequency	6	5	10	5
Percentage	23.10%	19.23%	38.64%	11.54%

5. I was more eager to do the in-class tasks than usual.				
Frequency	7	6	10	3
Percentage	29.43%	23.10%	38.64%	11.54%

6. I learned more than I usually do.				
Frequency	8	16	2	8
Percentage	30.87%	61.64%	7.78%	0

Table 8 shows that students' evaluations of digital multimedia instruction and teaching were generally positive. When it comes to the statements that deal with motivational components, most students rated them as "I agree," and nobody chose the "I completely agree" option. The first statement, "I preferred learning by watching recorded explanations better than listening to the explanations in class," indicates that students were generally satisfied with the information as it was presented in the video, despite the fact that their ratings for the information they had learned were mostly "I partly agree."

The proportion of students who agreed, disagreed, and totally agreed with this statement was the same. Just 7.78% of the students disagreed with this statement. Questioned the motivation to work in particular in relation to the second statement, "My motivation for work was higher." The incentive to work does not seem to be significantly higher when employing multimedia instruction and teaching style in comparison to traditional instruction. Only 15.38% of students agreed completely with the statement that the multimedia education and teaching technique increased students' enthusiasm to work compared to 20.13% who disagreed and 30.87% who

agreed or partially agreed. Were interested in knowing if the children thought it was easier to understand the video's subject than it was in class in light of the third comment, "It was easier to follow the explanations in the video than at school." found that 30.87% of students fully agreed with this statement, and 46.15% of students agreed, suggesting that students were able to follow the material more easily in the video than in the classroom. The following comment, "The classes that were done face-to-face were more interesting than usual," indicates that the students thought the material covered in class was engaging. We were interested to find out. It was found that 38.64% of students agreed with this statement. Additionally, 19.45% of students strongly agreed, suggesting that they thought school lessons were more engaging.

Nonetheless, a non-negligible proportion of students 23.10 per cent disapproved of this statement. For the fifth statement, "I was more eager to solve the in-class tasks than usual," we were curious to see if students preferred using the multimedia instruction and teaching technique over tackling the assignments using the standard format. We found that while 29.43% of the students disagreed with the statement, a sizable majority of the students 38.64% agreed with it. More captivating instructional approach, Were interested in knowing if the students felt that the digital multimedia teaching and learning approach had taught them more than the traditional one in reference to the last statement, "I learned more than I usually do." only 7.78% of students agreed with this statement. Completely, but the majority of students 61.64 per cent only partially agreed. In the second section, we aimed to find out if students would be receptive to multimedia-based instruction and learning in the future. Students may choose to answer "yes" or "no" to this question. Eighty-seven per cent of students expressed a desire to see more classes employ multimedia instruction and teaching methods in the third and most entertaining section. Additionally, it was hoped to see if this would increase student participation in the classroom. To be more precise, there were two responses to this question: either they would participate more than they currently do or they would participate less than they currently do. Found that 53.85% of students, a slightly higher percentage, stated they would participate more. If more classes were taught with a multimedia instruction and teaching approach, they would perform better than they do now. What the students liked and didn't like about the digital multimedia instruction and teaching approach is the subject of the fourth section of the survey

.Table 9: The students' most frequently mentioned benefits of digital multimedia instruction and teaching

Positive aspects	Frequency
Can hear explanation several times	9
Can stop the video	8
Less time is needed for contact treatment(video is short)	6
More cooperation	3

Out of the 26 students that participated in the survey, only four mentioned at least one unfavourable aspect of the digital multimedia instruction and teaching methodology. Three of them expressed frustration about not being allowed to ask the teacher questions while they were watching the video. Overall, the program's advantages were given considerably more weight by the students than its disadvantages. Based on the students' responses, one can deduce that they find schoolwork enjoyable and that they comprehend the material covered in the movie more easily.

The success of the issue's presentation through the film is further evidenced by the students' emphasis on the ability to watch the video and its explanation multiple times as a benefit of multimedia instruction and teaching. Students who participated in the study also emphasised a related advantage of digital multimedia instruction. Similar drawbacks of digital multimedia instruction and teaching were also mentioned by research participants' questions. One such drawback is that when learning the material through videos, students are unable to ask the teacher questions at home. This is one of the shortcomings of the teaching and learning approach based on multimedia..

Without an instructor present to pinpoint problems and provide solutions, it is very difficult to understand the basic concepts being taught. Observed that one disadvantage of digital multimedia instruction and teaching is that students can't always contact their teachers for assistance, which is similar to our observations. They believe that teaching children how to watch videos at the beginning of the school year that has the best possible

presentation of the material is an easy way to solve this problem. This entails giving them instructions to write down any questions they have for the teacher and to take notes while they watch.

The teacher should allot some time at the beginning of the lesson to answer these particular questions from the students. One of the main conclusions of the research conducted by Xiu, Y., & Thompson, P. (2020) is that teachers need to "model, encourage, and monitor students' before-class preparation to make sure they're prepared for in class activities, with which they scaffold student's success in a digitally-based learning environment. "The intriguing fact that the students weren't in the second post-test, despite the fact that their knowledge held up better, may also be highlighted. Based on their evaluations of the statement "I learned more than I usually do," the students tended to disagree.

However, similar to some earlier studies, the research (Xiu, Y., & Thompson, P., 2020) yielded conflicting results regarding their desire for this kind of implementation to continue. Students voiced dissatisfaction with multimedia instruction and teaching, preferring traditional implementation instead, according to research by Sommer and Ritzhaupt (2018). The investigation also found no discernible difference in academic achievement between traditional implementation and digital multimedia instruction and teaching. Mention additional negative aspects of the approach, such as students' challenges taking personal responsibility for their own education and participating in class discussions.

Our study's findings provide insight into how well instruction and multimedia work in various learning contexts. Based on the encouraging outcomes of the second post-test, these findings motivate maths teachers in Slovenia as well as educators in other fields to use multimedia instruction and teaching more broadly. More proof of this comes from the students' favourable perceptions of the approach. Finally, the research findings can help teacher educators plan undergraduate learning processes and teacher preparation programmes.

Results and Discussion

. Notably, they only talked about this strategy's one flaw that is, the inability to ask the teacher. This disadvantage could be easily remedied by offering more detailed guidelines on how to watch videos and learn. Were unable to identify the reason behind the experimental group's students' knowledge being more resilient than the control group's knowledge through our investigation. The chance to see and hear the explanation of the lesson material multiple times may have been what the students themselves identified is one of the benefits of digital multimedia instruction and teaching (it It's crucial to remember that the students no longer had the learning material available after the post-test and therefore could not view it before the second post-test).

Retention of the material may also be impacted by the practical work approach taken in in-person classes, which aimed to assist students in applying the material in a more real-world setting. The poll suggests that respondents were content with this approach, which may aid in knowledge retention. Due to the experimental conditions, it was not possible to fully isolate the digital multimedia education and teaching component of the study..

There was no way to prevent the experiment's participants from interacting and exchanging thoughts and experiences because they were classmates and fellow students. However, the fact that students participated in an experiment at school shows that they had a general incentive to participate in the research activities. Given the previously mentioned limitations of the study and the reality that there is no one correct method for integrating digital multimedia learning and teaching,

Because the findings do not apply to all subjects, all schools, or even all of the content in mathematics, the effects on students' perceptions, knowledge retention, and academic achievement primarily depend on the particular learning activities. When incorporating multimedia instruction and teaching in their classrooms, teachers may find the findings to be helpful or alarming. Subsequent investigations ought to concentrate on pinpointing the component that ensures superior information retention in digital multimedia-based instruction and learning compared to conventional approaches.

Conclusion

. The study conclusions deepen our knowledge of multimedia instruction, a relatively recent pedagogical innovation in education. They specifically highlight the contribution digital multimedia instruction and training make to the dissemination of superior knowledge, especially with regard to knowledge retention. Furthermore, students' positive opinions of this kind of instruction are evidence of its effectiveness. Student's chances of being ready for lifelong learning are enhanced when they have recurring positive experiences with the learning process. Nonetheless, the findings demonstrated a statistically significant difference in the two groups

knowledge retention. The group that received instruction using digital multimedia instruction and teaching approach retained more subject-matter knowledge than the group that was instructed using the traditional method. The study also revealed that the students were happy with this approach and wanted to see more creative teaching strategies like this one used in subsequent classes.

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